

The bilingual advantage: Where we are and where to next.

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Evidence is now persuasive towards a bilingual advantage and adaptations in human cognition once a higher degree of bilingualism is established. However, contradictory evidence exists in supporting an advantage for bilingual students in mathematical attainment and there are no clear explanations for this etiology. Examining the executive function (EF) aspect may provide some valuable insights into the bilingual advantage, particularly with young children. While broader research has supported an EF advantage for bilingual children, there is a dearth in the cognitive literature within the discipline of mathematics education and younger learners. Concerns have also been raised in relation to the limitations of the research designs of many of the studies that currently exist. This paper examines some current research and where we are currently, while suggesting some key considerations for future research in this area. Some recommendations include the need to examine the underlying basis for positive outcomes relating to bilingualism and impact on mathematics attainment, with a focus on ambitious longitudinal studies to establish reliability of claims being made.

Keywords: Executive Function, Mathematics, Bilingualism, Young Children

Introduction

Approximately half of the world's children are raised in bilingual or multilingual homes. The Irish education system naturally caters for bilingual learning through the promotion of heritage language (Irish) medium education (immersion education) alongside mainstream English-medium education. Of particular interest in this context is the network of "Gaelscoil" primary schools across the country, who operate in the medium of Irish day-to-day but are in English-speaking communities. Currently, 8% of the primary school population in the Republic of Ireland learn through the medium of Irish and there has been a 28% increase in enrolments in Gaelscoileanna since 2010. With increasing migration and displacement, our mathematics classrooms are also becoming more diverse in terms of languages and cultures.

Evidence is now persuasive towards a bilingual advantage and adaptations in human cognition once a higher degree of bilingualism is established (Bialystok, 2018). However, contradictory evidence exists in supporting an advantage for bilingual students in mathematical attainment and there are no clear explanations for this etiology. Therefore, pedagogically, challenges exist in terms of catering for bi-/multi-lingual learners, and moreover, helping them reach their full mathematical potential. Although little is known about the connection between bilingualism and mathematical achievement in children (just that there is one), what has been established is the positive impact of bilingualism on executive function (EF) (Bialystok, 2018), a multifaceted set of mental skills inclusive of working memory, flexible thinking, and self-control (Miyake et al., 2000). I suggest that we need to revisit the conclusion made by Peal and Lambert (1962), the first researchers to provide reliable evidence of a cognitive bilingual advantage:

The results of this study indicate the value of shifting emphasis from looking for favorable or unfavorable effects of bilingualism on intelligence to an inquiry into the basic nature of these effects. Perhaps further research may profit from this different emphasis. (p. 21)

This recommendation has yet to be realised to its full potential in general bilingual educational research and more specifically, in mathematics education research. Examining the EF aspect may provide some valuable insights into the bilingual advantage, particularly with young children, where significant development of EF skills is evident.

Executive Function, Mathematics and Bilingualism

Executive function relates to a set of cognitive processes that guide behaviours on tasks essential to learning, through a contribution to self-monitoring and regulation processes (Baggetta & Alexander, 2016). The most rapid development of these EF processes occurs in the early childhood years (Clements et al., 2016). Numerous studies with children have consistently demonstrated that bilingual children outperform monolingual children on well-established and validated battery tests associated with EF skills. These include inhibitory control (Simon Task, see e.g., Antoniou et al., 2016; Morales et al., 2013; flanker tests, see e.g., Costa et al., 2009; Attention Network Test, see e.g., Yang & Yang, 2016); mental set-switching (Dimensional Change Card Sort, see e.g., Carlson & Meltzoff, 2008; colour-shape task, see e.g., Barac & Bialystok, 2012); and working memory (complex span tasks, see e.g., Sorge et al., 2016). Similarly, studies focused on brain-imaging of infants and children demonstrate that acquiring two languages facilitates the cortical and subcortical brain regions operations that are associated with EF (see e.g., Arredondo et al., 2017; Krizman et al., 2015; Ramírez et al., 2016). From a bilingual education perspective, Nicolay and Ponclet (2015) found greater advantages in EF for 5-year-old children participating in a 3-year language immersion programme, than for the monolingual control group. Therefore, we can propose that acquiring two languages in early childhood can contribute to differences in EF between bilingual and monolingual children (Moreno et al., 2015).

Similarly, research has demonstrated a relationship between EF and mathematical skills. In order to solve mathematics problems, key cognitive resources are required. One essential resource is EF (Clements et al., 2016; Cragg et al., 2017). For example, working memory is required for remembering answers to different parts, when working out the solution to a complex problem (Cragg & Gilmore, 2014). Similarly, the EF processes of shifting and inhibiting have been found to be essential for mathematical achievement (Bull & Lee, 2014). Other essential resources for solving mathematics problems are domain-specific such as mathematical proficiencies (Cragg et al., 2017). Accordingly, several key researchers have offered a multi-component model to explain the skills underpinning mathematics inclusive of both cognitive processes and domain-specific mathematical knowledge (e.g., Geary, 2011). These frameworks include reference to mathematical procedures and concepts, and how they draw upon linguistic and spatial skills and in particular EF processes to support mathematics attainment. Therefore, these models suggest that EF is negotiated through

domain-specific mathematical skills (Cragg et al., 2017) and that many elements contribute to mathematics ability (Geary, 2011).

Interestingly, longitudinal studies indicate that the connection between EF and mathematical attainment is one-directional, that is, EF contributes to the development of mathematical abilities, but mathematical abilities do not contribute to enhancing EF (Clark et al., 2010). Addendum to this, causal evidence of interventions designed to develop EF and accordingly increase mathematical achievement are weak (Jacob & Parkinson, 2015). Clements et al. (2016) conclude that developing both EF processes and mathematical proficiencies is essential for young children. They theorize several pedagogical mathematical activities that may support the development of EF, that is creating a bidirectional relationship, but conclude that much more research and developmental work is needed in creating high-quality mathematics education that would have a twofold benefit for mathematics attainment and EF processes. Given the well-established link between mathematics achievement and EF, I posit that the advantages in EF evident in bilingual children could impart benefits for mathematical cognition and ability for all students.

Most recently, work by Hartanto et al. (2018), when controlling for key covariates (e.g., demographic, socioeconomic status), found a positive relationship between bilingualism and mathematical competence for 4–7-year-olds. Similarly, Marian et al. (2013) examined the impact of a two-way immersion programme that combined English (majority language) with Spanish (minority language) on third, fourth and fifth grade students' performance on a State Standards Achievement Test. Findings demonstrate that bilingual students outperform monolingual students. However, when controlling for students from lower socio-economic backgrounds, this correlation was weakened. An fMRI study undertaken by Stocco and Pract (2014) found that bilingual students were significantly faster than matched monolingual students on tasks that required cognitive flexibility to combine arithmetic operations. Kempert et al.'s (2011) study illustrates the importance of bilingual students' (age 8) language proficiency for performance on more demanding mathematical word problems. When controlling for socio-economic backgrounds and cognitive and arithmetic ability, interestingly monolinguals outperformed bilingual students on simple word problems. However, this was not the case for more challenging word problems with distractors. It is possible to conjecture that the nature of the mathematical experiences of young bilingual children may impact on EF development, but a significant research gap remains in relation to understanding the EF advantages associated with bilingual children and connected benefits for mathematics learning.

Some key considerations

Both positive and null results in terms of the correlation between bilingualism and cognitive advantage continue to be reported (Gunnerud et al., 2020) suggesting some further factor(s) may be involved in the variable outcomes. Of note, previous studies have generally been restricted by limitations in the research design and methods, for example, sample size, age of participants, not controlling for key variables such as socio-economic status and

language use, a focus on clinical settings, and single measurements of mathematics ability (Hartanto et al., 2018). In view of children’s rapid cognitive development in pre-school/early primary, Hartanto et al. (2018) identify that “methodologically rigorous large-scale studies are vital” (p. 218) and should be longitudinal in design to establish reliability (Castillo et al., 2020).

Bialystok (2018) argues that the contradictory evidence in relation to the relationship between bilingualism and EF can be attributed to an “over-simplification” (p. 285) of the two concepts. The typical methodological approach employed to measure bilingualism tends to be language-type assessments. However, this portrays language and bilingualism as a categorical variable, that is limited and having a fixed number of possible values and assigning participants to a bilingual or monolingual group. Bialystok (2018) contends that this is “problematic for bilingualism: there is no agreed cutoff point determining when knowledge of another language is sufficient to designate “bilingualism”, thereby introducing large variation into each group.” (p. 285). She suggests that bilingual experience needs to be examined and taken into consideration when assigning participants to groups within a study in terms of degree of bilingualism. Accordingly, language proficiency tests, background information and language use/experiences should be examined in order to measure bilingualism and to group participants (Comishen & Bialystok, 2021). Taking such an approach to defining and measuring bilingualism may contribute to understanding the longitudinal relationship and to unpacking the causal relationship between bilingualism and mathematical cognition.

Similarly, EF is a complex construct that is difficult to examine, with many models currently existing (Bialystok, 2018). The most utilised model in bilingual research is that of Miyake et al. (2000), yet it has not proved to be effective at capturing differences between bilingual and monolingual learners (Bialystok, 2018). Bialystok (2018) argues for a focus on executive ‘attention’ which can be viewed as a continuous construct and would allow for examining how experience (e.g., classroom) impacts on the executive system and its functioning. This results in a focus on adaptation rather than transfer and I suggest that by combining both qualitative and quantitative measures as related to language experiences, EF will contribute to exposing the etiology of the relationship between bilingualism and mathematical cognition and lead to significant educational research breakthroughs.

Education itself is a multidisciplinary endeavour and multidisciplinary approaches are utilised in undertaking educational research. Challenges also persist with implementing novel methodologies in classroom settings and implementing such approaches with young children (Bhavnani et al., 2021). One such approach may be real time continuous monitoring of physiological cognitive responses (e.g. eye tracking, EEG) merged with observations of mathematics classroom experiences. Generally, cognitive neuroscience research is conducted in controlled laboratory settings. Such settings bear little resemblance to classroom and educational settings where key learning and development takes place. The use of traditional cognitive neuroscience methods in real-world social settings is starting to emerge due to the development of portable devices. However, these devices have a significant cost attached to them, as well as a specialised skillset in using them (Diiker et al., 2017). Nevertheless,

Bhavnani et al. (2021) stresses the need for moving outside highly controlled settings and using multi-disciplinary research groups to undertake such cognitive neuroscience research in social settings to reap the benefits of such frontier research and its implementation at scale.

Where to next

There has been a focus more on the social aspect of learning rather than the cognitive impact of bilingualism within mathematics education research (Ní Ríordáin & Flanagan, 2022). If we are to examine in more detail the cognitive advantages of bilingualism and ultimately exploiting that advantage for learners, then we need to consider novel research designs and methodological approaches that facilitate such an exploration *in classrooms* and overcome key methodological limitations identified in previous studies (Bhavnani et al., 2021; Hartanto et al., 2018). This will involve connecting objective cognitive measures with phenomenological classroom data (Delahunty et al., 2018) and a design that is longitudinal in implementation. Such an approach would require a multidisciplinary approach and methodology that has never been utilised in the intended manner to examine bilingual mathematics learners; that is utilising and combining clinical approaches (such as EEG, heartrate and electrodermal measurement, eye tracking) with phenomenological data in classroom settings (rather than clinical/lab settings). Such educational settings and longitudinal studies carry high-risk and challenges (Diiker et al., 2017). If a conceptual link can be demonstrated and established, it would provide evidence of the cognitive etiology of the bilingual advantage as a ‘lived’ manifestation in young children, within the classroom environment. In particular, it could lead to a new understanding of the ways in which language(s) and EF interact and support mathematics attainment and to create advantages for bilingual learners. This new understanding can then influence pedagogic interventions that aim to capitalise on this relationship (Cragg et al., 2017) and to improve the mathematical outcomes for bilingual learners. Interventions in the early years provide the optimal opportunity for child development (Bhavnani et al., 2021). Moreover, it may provide some inwards in identifying “the basic nature of these effects” (Peal & Lambert, 1962, p.21) and conducting frontier research to provide a causal explanation for bilingualism and its impact on mathematics attainment.

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